

Knowledge, Attitude and Adherence to Dietary Regimen among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus as Measure for Glycemic Control

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Abstract

Background: Diabetes Mellitus is a metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of glucose in the blood that has attracted global health concern due to its high rate of incidence, health complications and risk factors. Diabetic patients frequently face difficulty in identifying and adhering to dietary regimen, including its quality and quantity. **Purpose:** This study assessed the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus as measure for glycemic control in Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara. The objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge on dietary regimen, attitude to dietary regimen, adherence to dietary regimen, and the measure to improve knowledge, attitude and adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients. **Method:** Descriptive survey design was used for the study. Convenience sampling technique and a sample size of 150 was used. Self-developed questionnaire was administered. Data was collected, analyzed and presented in tables. Frequency count, percentages, average mean and odd ratio probability test was used as method for statistical analysis. **Results:** Findings from the study revealed knowledge on dietary regimen for diabetes among diabetic patients centered on diet specifications (80%), and that sugar should be completely avoided (74.6%). Meanwhile, based on attitude to dietary regimen among diabetic patients, majority of the respondents accepted that keeping to dietary regimen for managing diabetes difficult (61.3%). **Conclusions:** Our study therefore revealed that diabetic patients often find difficulty in adhering to the prescribed regimen not undermining that there is high knowledge base on dietary regimen. The accepted causes of non-adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients included; ignorance, lack of family support, finance, not being able to eat other food, and too many instructions to follow. Hence, it is important that the identified measures to promote positive attitude to dietary regimen among diabetic patients such as; family and group support, mass campaign and sensitization, and enlightenment programs be adopted to enhance management outcomes.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Adherence, Dietary, Regimen, Diabetes mellitus.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a major public health problem and is emerging as a pandemic(1). The fundamental cause of obesity and overweight is an energy imbalance between calories consumed and calories burned up (2). Diabetes is one such disease known to give patients false sense of well-being even with hyperglycemia, and unless patient understands the importance of adherence to dietary regimen it is difficult to prevent complications due to diabetes mellitus (3). Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease is characterized by elevated levels of glucose in

the blood as a result of insulin deficiency or the inaction of insulin present, resulting in disruption of normal carbohydrates, fat and protein metabolism and the development over time of micro-vascular and macro-vascular complications and neuropathies (4). The criteria for diagnosis of diabetes mellitus have been explained and include a causal plasma glucose of 11.1mmo1/L or higher, or fasting plasma glucose of 7.0mmo1/L or higher(5).

Type 2 diabetes or non-insulin-dependent or adult-onset diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder that results in hyperglycaemia due to the body's ineffectiveness in using the insulin produced by the

pancreas (6). It is a complex, chronic illness requiring incessant medical care with multifactorial risk-reduction strategies beyond glycemic control. Type 2 diabetes accounts for the vast majority of people with diabetes around the world (7). While type 2 diabetes is the more prevalent form and results from insulin resistance with a defect in compensatory insulin secretion. The effects of diabetes mellitus include long-term damage, dysfunction and failure of various organs (8). Diabetes mellitus of type 2 class may present with characteristic symptoms such as; thirst, polyuria, blurring of vision, and weight loss. In its most severe forms, ketoacidosis or a non-ketotic hyperosmolar state may develop and lead to stupor, coma and, in absence of effective treatment, death (9). The long-term effects of type 2 diabetes mellitus include; progressive development of the specific complications of retinopathy with potential blindness, nephropathy that may lead to renal failure, and/or neuropathy with risk of foot ulcers, amputation, Charcot joints, and features of autonomic dysfunction, including sexual dysfunction(10). People with type 2 diabetes mellitus are at increased risk of cardiovascular, peripheral vascular and cerebrovascular disease (11).

The rise in prevalence of diabetes mellitus is predicted to be much greater in developing than in developed countries. In Nigeria, majority of type 2 diabetic patients do not adhere to lifestyle modifications because they feel they are being punished as a result of dietary regimen. This has affected the outcome of the treatment they receive as they take food they have been restricted to take for some time. Knowledge, awareness and adherence to dietary regimen is critical in controlling glycemic problems in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus, were these variables are limited, glycemic control becomes difficult resulting in complications linked to morbidity and mortality. Because the risk of complications of type 2 diabetes mellitus can be reduced by proper adherence, patient non-adherence to treatment recommendations is often frustrating for type 2 diabetes mellitus health care professionals (2). Despite the treatment guidelines and drugs available for the treatment of patients having type 2 diabetes,

bringing their blood glucose level under control has often pose a challenge. In spite of many advances made in adherence interventions, adherence rates have remained nearly unchanged in the last decades (12). As a result of this widespread adherence problem, substantial numbers of patients do not get the maximum benefit of medical treatment - with poor health outcomes, lower quality of life and increased health care costs as a result. The impact of poor adherence is felt even more as the burden of patients with chronic diseases grows worldwide (13).

For an excellent life the patients suffering with chronic problem should adhere to the treatment guidelines in strict compliance. Physical activity is one of the mainstay clinical interventions for preventing metabolic diseases, and dietary habits are the primary factor for the rapidly rising incidence of DM. Reducing weight and maintaining a healthy weight, reducing energy intake, and food intake high in vegetables, fruit, whole grains, legumes, nuts, and dairy products are core parts of management (9). Continuing patient self-management education and support are critical to averting acute complications such as hypoglycemia, diabetic coma, diabetic ketoacidosis, and reducing the risk of long-term complications such as diabetic nephropathy, diabetic neuropathy, diabetic cardiomyopathy (13). The researchers were prompted to carry out this study after a close neighbor died of type 2 diabetes mellitus because she refused to comply with treatment regimen and decided to take lots of carbonated drinks for a period of time. This study was therefore undertaken to assess the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen in a teaching hospital as measure for glycemic control among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Methods

Research Design

The research design used was descriptive survey method. This study obtained descriptive data about the research variables relating to the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus as measure for glycemic control in Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara within a defined study period. This design was considered useful in gathering elicited information about the characteristics within a particular field of study and provides the picture of situations as they naturally happen.

Study setting

The study setting was Delta State University teaching hospital, Oghara, Delta State (popularly known as

DELSUTH). Delta State University Teach Hospital was inaugurated on the 10th of June, 2020 by His Excellency, Good luck Jonathan, the former president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, with a mandate to provide tertiary health care through training of undergraduate medical students of Delta State University, Abraka. The facility was located at Oghara in Ethiopie West Local Government Area of Delta State, South East, Nigeria.

Target Participants

The target population of the study include; type 2 diabetic patients attending DELSUTH Oghara, Delta State. Information about the patients was obtained from the record department of the hospital. The total population of one hundred and fifty (240) registered diabetic patients were obtained from the hospital record as at the time of the study, from which the sample size was determined.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study was calculated using the Slovin's method which is as follows; $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ where; n is sample size, N is population size, and e is level of precision which is usually 0.10, 0.05, or 0.01 (i.e. 10%, 5% or 1%). Using a level of precision of 5% and the population size of 240 as shown below; $n = \frac{240}{1 + 240(0.05)^2} = 150$

Therefore, the sample size was 150 patients suffering from diabetes mellitus in DELSUTH Oghara, Delta State. The purposive sampling technique was used by the researcher in selecting the sample size.

Ethical Consideration

A letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Nursing Science, Delta State University, Abraka to the medical director of the hospital. Approval was sought from the institutional ethics committee for the research to be conducted (Permit No.: RBC/FBMC/DELSU/23/299). Consent to participate was duly obtained from each participants, the topic under study was clearly explained to them and they were allowed to willingly make their decision. Anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents was ensured by administering simple questionnaire that did not intrude into their privacy by not including subjects name and identity. Information was held confidential.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

All patients suffering from diabetes mellitus of type 2 conditions in DELSUTH Oghara, Delta State and whose consents were obtained were recruited as participants for the study. Diabetes mellitus patients in DELSUTH Oghara who declined to participate in the study and those with other types of DM were excluded. *Research instrument*

A self-administered questionnaire was designed by the researcher and was used as the instrument for this study. The questionnaire had multiple choice questions with 'Yes', 'No' and the 'Don't Know' options. The researcher presented copy of the research instrument to the supervisor for proper scrutiny. The instrument was validated by 2 research experts in Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Delta State University Abraka for face and construct validity.

Data Collection Procedure

Copies of the research instrument was administered to the participant with the aid of two trained research assistants using face-to-face method. All the participants were explained about the purpose of the study. The researchers went to the hospital, administered the questionnaires and obtained relevant data for the study. The researchers used the highest degree of skills and care in carrying out this research, the researcher also ensured to use scientifically skilled hands at every stage of the job.

Statistical analysis

Data collected was analyzed for frequency counts and percentages to examine knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The statistical tool used for testing the hypothesis was the odd ratio probability for cases and control at p-value <0.05 level of significance. The data collected were entered into Excel spread sheets, and analysis was carried out using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows, Version 11.0. Findings were presented in distribution tables.

Results

From Table 1, 8%of respondents were between ages 25-30 years, 16.7% were of ages 31-35 years, 20% were between 36-40 years of age, 25.3% were between ages 41-45 years and 30% were of 46 years and above. 83.3% of respondents were Christians, 10% were Muslims and 6.7% were traditional worshippers. 43.3% of the respondents Urhobos/Isokos, 34.7% were Ibos/Ukwani's, 22% were from other tribes. 18.7% of the respondents were single, 40.7% were married, 10% were separated, 5.3% were cohabiting and 25.3% were widows/widowers. Among the respondents, 42% were males while 58% were

females. Also, 9.3% of the respondents had no formal education, 14.7% had primary education while majority of the respondents had secondary education (31.3%). 16% were HND holders while 10% had B.Sc certification. Majority of the respondents were self-employed (42.7%) while 24% and 33.3% were unemployed and employed respectively. The findings from Table 2 revealed that 120(80%) of the respondents have knowledge on dietary regimen adherence as a method of management in diabetes mellitus, while 20(20%) do not have adequate knowledge. 58(38.7%) of the respondents support that diabetes diet is a healthy diet for most people, 81(54.7%) does not support, and 11(7.3%) don't know. In item 3, 64(42.7%) believes that carbohydrate diet should be completely avoided in the management of diabetes, 52(34.7%) believes it should not be completely avoided, while 34(22.7%) don't know if it should be avoided or not. 32(21.3%) of the respondents believes that unsweetened fruit juice raises blood glucose levels, 94(62.7%) believes it does not, while 24(16%) are indecisive. 98(55.3%) of the respondents does not believe using olive oil in cooking can help lower blood cholesterol level, 20(13.3%) believes it helps lower blood cholesterol level while 32(21.3%) do not know. 102(68%) of the respondents are of the opinion that a can of soft drink cannot be taken often while managing diabetes, 18(12%) believes it can be taken whereas, 30(20%) do not know. 55(36.7%) of the respondents usually attend diabetes classes while 95(63.3%) do not attend. 112(74.6%) of the respondents agrees that excess sugar should be avoided while managing diabetes, 26(17.3%) did not agree, while 12(8%) were indecisive. Finally, 51(34%) of the respondents agrees that fruits and vegetables are healthy diet for diabetes, 66(44%) believes it can be taken whereas, 33(22%) do not know.

From table 3, 52(34.7%) of the respondents still eat the diets they were counselled not to eat, 98(65.3%) abstained from the diets they were counselled not to eat. 65(43.3%) believed that diet control is as important as drugs in the management of diabetes while, 85(56.7%) believed that diet control is not as important as drugs in the management of diabetes. 92(61.3%) found keeping to dietary regimen

difficult while 58(38.7%) that does not find it difficult. 82(54.7%) of the respondents always keep to the diets they are advised to eat while 68(45.3%) that do not always keep to diet as advised. 106(70%) of the respondents avoid intake of excess sugar, while 44(29.3%) do not avoid intake of excess sugar.

From table 4, the findings revealed that 94(62.3%) of the respondents perceived ignorance as the cause of non-adherence to dietary regimen while 56(37.3%) does not. 95(63.3%) viewed lack of family support as a cause for non-adherence to dietary regimen while 55(36.7%) did not perceive it as a cause. 110(73.3%) of the respondents agreed that finance is a cause for non-adherence to dietary regimen, while 40(26.7%) rejected the opinion. 89(59.3%) saw the opinion that not being able to eat other food as a cause for non-adherence to dietary regimen, while 61(40.7%) did not see it as a cause. 58(38.7%) saw social gatherings as a cause, while 92(61.3%) failed to see it as a cause. Finally, 88(58.7%) of the respondents viewed too many instructions to follow as a cause for non-adherence, while 62(41.3%) had contrary opinion.

From table 5, all the respondents 150 (100%) believes that family support would serve as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients in the management of diabetes. 98(65.3%) of the respondents believes that mass campaign would serve as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen while 52(34.7%) do not believe mass campaign would serve as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen. 120(80%) of the respondents are of the opinion that support groups will serve as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients while 30(20%) do not think mass campaign would serve as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen. 108(72%) of the respondents see enlightenment programs as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen among patients having diabetes while 42(28%) do not see enlightenment programs as a measure to promote adherence to dietary regimen.

Table 6 shows the testing of hypothesis between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen among diabetic patients in DELSUTH, Oghara. It was revealed from the table that a p-value of 0.002 which was smaller than the level of significance set at $P < 0.05$, confirmed that there is significant relationship between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen. Thus, the hypothesis which stated that "there is a significant relationship between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen" was accepted.

Discussion

From this study, it was observed that majority of the respondents have adequate knowledge on adherence to dietary regimen as a method of management in diabetes mellitus. Majority also, are knowledgeable on the need for avoidance of excessive sugar (carbohydrate) as a form of dietary modification. However, most participant are not aware that cooking with olive oil can help reduce blood cholesterol level which is essential for the control of diabetes. Data from our study showed that there is more to be done to help increase the already existent knowledge on dietary regimen for diabetes. In a study carried out by Ghazanfari et al. (14) a significant improvement in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the intervention group toward healthy behaviors regarding nutrition, physical activity, and self care. Study also carried out by Shareef et al. (15) reported a significant increase in overall diabetes knowledge from 18.05% to 25.43% in the intervention group compared to controls. Similarly, evidences from previous studies suggest that adequate knowledge of diabetes mellitus help to achieve better glycemic control and prevent comorbidity like diabetes and hypertension (16, 17, 18, 19, 20).

Data on attitude captured in Table 3 of our study revealed that most of the respondents found keeping to dietary regimen for managing diabetes difficult despite the high statistics of those who has knowledge on dietary regimen for diabetes, always keep to diets they are advised to eat, and avoid intake of excess sugar. It was equally revealed that most diabetic patients often sometimes eat diets they are required not to eat, thus, it difficulty in adhere to the prescribed regimen. Our study is consistent with the position of previous studies that emphasized that there is a dire need of better health information to change the attitude and practices of public regarding diabetes through large scale sensitization and awareness programs (16,21). Findings from Table 4 representing statement on the causes of non-adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients, it was gathered that the highest response was gathered from finance, whereas, the least accepted cause was social gathering.

This agrees with the view of Adisa et al. (22) who conducted a qualitative study and identified financial limitation an important cause of non-adherence to diabetes medications.

Regarding measures to promote adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients as revealed in Table 5, the highest responses were attributed to family support, this was followed by support group and enlightenment programs, while the least measure was found in mass campaign. According to the study of Rezaei et al. (23) family support can certainly play a significant role in reducing the pressure on the diabetic patients. Similarly, findings from Table 6, relating to relationship between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen revealed that a p-value of 0.002 which was less than the level of significance set at $P < 0.05$, confirmed that there is significant relationship between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen. Thus, the hypothesis which stated that "there is a significant relationship between the knowledge and attitude to dietary regimen" was accepted. This is in line with a research carried out by previous study that reported that less respondents adhere to dietary regimen seriously, while majority held the view that adherence to dietary regimen is not important in the management of diabetes (24,25).

Conclusion

Diabetes mellitus as a chronic illness require a lifetime of special self-management behaviours. This study examined the knowledge, attitude and adherence to dietary regimen among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus as measure for glycemic control. Findings revealed that diabetic patients often find difficulty in adhering to the prescribed regimen not undermining that there is high knowledge base on dietary regimen. The accepted causes of non-adherence to dietary regimen among diabetic patients included; ignorance, lack of family support, finance, not being able to eat other food, and too many instructions to follow. Hence, it is important that the identified measures to promote positive attitude to dietary regimen among diabetic patients such as; family and group support, mass campaign and sensitization, and enlightenment programs be adopted to enhance management outcomes.

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Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Diabetic Patients

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age (years)</i>		
25-30	12	8.0
31-35	25	16.7
36-40	30	20.0
41-45	38	25.3
46-above	45	30.0
Total	150	100
<i>Religion</i>		
Christianity	125	83.3
Muslims	15	10.0
Traditional Worshippers	10	6.7
Total	150	100
<i>Ethnicity</i>		
Urhobo/Isoko	65	43.3
Ibo/Ukwani	52	34.7
Others	33	22.0
Total	150	100
<i>Marital status</i>		
Single	28	18.7
Married	61	40.7
Separated	15	10.0
Cohabiting	8	5.3
Widow/Widower	38	25.3
Total	150	100
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	63	42.0
Female	87	58.0
Total	150	100
<i>Level of Education</i>		
No formal Education	14	9.3
Primary	22	14.7
Secondary	47	31.3
Diploma	28	18.7
HND	24	16.0
Bsc	15	10.0
Total	150	100
<i>Occupation</i>		
Unemployed	36	24.0
Self-employed	64	42.7
Employed full time	50	33.3
Total	150	100

Table 2: Knowledge on Dietary Regimen for Diabetes among Diabetic Patients

S/N	Knowledge Items	YES	NO	DON'T KNOW
1	Watching your diet is a good way of controlling diabetes	120 (80%)	20 (20%)	0 (0%)
2	Diets for diabetic patients are healthy	58 (38.7%)	81 (54.7%)	11 (7.3%)
3	Carbohydrate diet should be completely avoided while managing Diabetes	64 (42.7%)	52 (34.7%)	34 (22.7%)
4	Unsweetened fruit juice raises blood glucose level	32 (21.3%)	94 (62.7%)	24 (16%)
5	Using Olive oil in cooking can help lower blood cholesterol level	20 (13.3%)	98 (65.3%)	32 (21.3%)
6	A can of soft drink can be taken while managing diabetes	18 (12%)	102 (68%)	30 (20%)
7	I usually attend diabetes classes	55 (36.7%)	95 (63.3%)	0 (0%)
8	Sugar should be completely avoided while managing diabetes	112 (74.6%)	26 (17.3%)	12 (8%)
9	Fruits and vegetables are healthy diet for diabetes	51 (34%)	66 (44%)	33 (22%)

Table 3: Attitude to Dietary Regimen among Diabetic Patients

S/N	Attitude Items	YES	NO
1	I sometimes eat diets I was required not to eat	52 (34.7%)	98 (65.3%)
2	Diet control are as important as drugs in the management of diabetes	65 (43.3%)	85 (56.7%)
3	Keeping to dietary regimen is difficult	92 (61.3%)	58 (38.7%)
4	I always keep to diets I am advised to eat	82 (54.7%)	68 (45.3%)
5	I avoid intake of excess sugar	106 (70.6%)	44 (29.3%)

Table 4: Causes of Non-adherence to Dietary Regimen among Diabetic Patients

Causes Items	YES	NO
Ignorance	94 (62.7%)	56 (37.3%)
Lack of family support	95 (63.3%)	55 (36.7%)
Finance	110 (73.3%)	40 (26.7%)
Not being able to eat other food	89 (59.3%)	61 (40.7%)
Social gathering	58 (38.7%)	92 (61.3%)
Too many Instructions to follow	88 (58.7%)	62 (41.3%)

Table 5: Measures to Promote Adherence to Dietary Regimen among Diabetic Patients

Measures Items	YES	NO
Family Support	150 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Mass campaign	98 (65.3%)	52 (34.7%)
Support groups	120 (80%)	30 (20%)
Enlightenment programs	108 (72%)	42 (28%)

Table 6: Relationship between the Knowledge and Attitude to Dietary Regimen

Knowledge on Dietary Regimen	n	Attitude to Dietary Regimen		
		OR	95%CI	p value
Watching your diet is a good way to control diabetes	120	3.212	0.111-5.313	0.001
Can of soft drink can be taken while managing diabetes	18	0.621	0.123-4.779	0.002
Eating fruits and vegetables are healthy for a diabetic patient	51	2.872	0.169-4.264	0.003
Unsweetened fruit juice causes diabetes	32	1.226	0.152-5.910	0.001
Sugar should be completely avoided by diabetic patients	112	3.331	0.157-6.131	0.001
Diets for diabetic patients are healthy	58	2.144	1.144-4.602	0.002
	p < 0.05			0.002

OR: Odds Ratio**CI: Confidence Interval****References**

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